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JHALRAPATAN — A GEOGRAPHICAL STUDY OF A MARKET CENTRE

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In India structure of market has so far been treated in their own purview by economists and commercialists, and that too, to a very limited extent. It might not be unfolding entire market ecology speaking in terms of spatial relationship and matrix of culture group. Disciplines related to market-phenomenon are yet to contribute something substantial in this field and geography is one of them. Synoptic treatment of market as a functional unit of the 'geosphere' is the major objective of the present paper and the authors have endeavoured to bring fourth the **geographic personality** of Jhalrapatan as a market centre.

Geospheric Setting:

Jhalrapatan (24°32'N and 76°10'E; nearly 1000 ft. above mean sea-level) is an old market of considerable importance on the Hadaoti plateau extending in the southeastern-most part of Rajas-

than. Its typical location on the border-land of two different physographic units viz., the low and discontinuous Malvi hills of sandstone and the westward extended high flat plain of the Malwa, provides impetus for its being developed as an important entrepot market. Geologically speaking while its adjoining area is occupied in the south by alluvium and in the north by Jhalrapatan sandstone, the town itself is originally founded in the narrow belt of the Deccan trap extending southeast to northwest. The town is surrounded by a region of very fertile soil facilitating thereby prosperous agricultural conditions meeting basic needs of the town as well as its service area alike.

The climate of Jhalrapatan is characterised by dry and hot summers and mild winters. The iso-

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hyet of 38" passes through the town and nearly 70% of the annual rainfall is registered in the two months of July and August. The uncertainty and variability both in amount and duration are some of the negative characteristics of the rainfall.

The locality because of fertile soil, less rugged terrain and favourable climatic conditions was formerly endowed with rich natural vegetation cover but most of which, only in the recent past, was devoured by settlements.

The location of Jhalrapatan has always been an important factor in its role as a central place or service centre (Fig. 2) It is only

57 miles to the south of Kota—the industrial hub and one of the major developing cities of the whole of India. Jaipur the State capital lies some 312 miles towards north, while Ujjain and Indore are 106 and 150 miles and the capital of M.P. is not far off being only 160 miles in the southeast of the market of Jhalrapatan. Speaking in terms of its immediate field of influence, it occupies a vantage point in a centre surrounded by a number of important markets or 'mandis'—the source places. The following table reveals locational value of Jhalrapatan among other markets of the surrounding area:

TABLE I

Locational value of Jhalrapatan among other markets of the surrounding area.

Sl. No.	Markets	Distance from Jhalrapatan in Kms.	Population in 1961	Daily No. of buses from and to Jhalrapatan
1.	Indore	194	394,941	2
2.	Bhopal	258	185,374	4
3.	Ujjain	258	144,161	2
4.	Kota	91	120,345	16
5.	Neemuch	144	36,287	2
6.	Baran	90	22,764	3
7.	Bhawanimandi	43	7,247	6
8.	Ramganjmandi	32	6,805	3
9.	Sunel	36	6,526	2
10.	Pirawa	58	5,997	4
11.	Aklera	46	4,527	10
12.	Dag	74	4,884	2
13.	Bakani	38	3,641	2
14.	Manoharthana	81	3,432	3

The evenly distribution of source places of different ranks of population in the surrounding region (Fig. 2) may be explained by stable and prosperous agricultural conditions because of the fertile 'mal', 'dhamani and coarse alluvium soils of the region drained by Kali-Sindh, Chandrabhaga and other numerous watercourses. This induces development of agricultural markets.

The actual site of Jhalrapatan is associated with the ancient site of Chandravati which is hardly a

furlong off on the river Chandrabhaga and is endowed both with water and natural defence as nodality of the routes.

Origin and Growth of Jhalrapatan as a central place:

Jhalrapatan seems a town of medieval origin and on the basis of gazetteerial account it was founded by Zalim Singh Jhala in 1796 A.D. but it was occupied originally by an ancient town of 'Chandravati' a short form of 'Chandra-bhagavati' meaning a

FIG. 2

town on the bank of the river Chandrabhaga.' Original 'settlement according to Cunningham belongs to 500-1000 B.C. which later on must have been capital of Ptolemy's district of 'Sandrabitis' in the beginning of the christian era.²The only specimen supporting the antiquity of the site is a group of about 13 temples still standing in their faded glory on the banks of the river Chandrabhaga. Jhalrapatan like other medieval settlements is a walled town with gates, rampart and a deep wide moat on the outer side. In its original phase of development every initiative was provided to attract population of far and near, and consequently, within a short span of 25 years the town was grown into an important trade and commerce entrepot for the entire northern part of the Malwa region. Its phenomenal growth, however, was hampered with the changing and shifting of the capital some four miles north from Jhalrapatan to Jhalawar in 1813. Secondly, with the opening up of the Mathura-Nagda Branch of Western Rly. in 1919, some new market centres appeared along the track such as Bhawanimandi, Ramganjmandi, etc., which too affected its growth adversely. But again, during the last two decades since independence its revival and regeneration as a market, how-

ever slow but steady, have become apparent. This resurgence may be explained largely by its nodality attained through various roads cart-tracks radiating from here in nearly all directions, thus connecting almost all the rural settlements of the surrounding countryside. The nodal situation of the market of Jhalrapatan, on the one hand, is responsible for the easy movement of the agricultural produce to and fro, and on the other, of its development as a regional trading centre.

Marketing and Structure of the Market: (Fig. 4):

Marketing is the main function of market centre and it is because of this function that its existence is explained geographically. It serves both the needs of local people as well as of the surrounding region. The process of marketing is completed by various markets — rural or urban, and also by various market-places, wholesale or retail, specialised or general etc. The geography is primarily concerned with spatial distribution, mapping and interpretation of market-places, in their functional aspect integrating the process of marketing into the whole. In other words, a market town is to be evaluated

both by formal and functional approaches.

(a) Wholesale Marketing—

The wholesale business in this

town is confined only to cloth and foodgrains. The town has a well developed cloth market and caters not only to the local needs but also to the surrounding rural

areas and smaller towns. Cloth is by the local dealers. But of the 33 imported directly from Bombay, cloth shops in the town only 5 Madras, Indore and Ahmedabad deal in wholesale marketing.

1. Imperial Gazetteer, vol. XIV p. 397.

2. Cunningham, A. Archaeological Survey of India. vol. II, p. 254.

The town is an important collecting centre of a large number of agricultural products such as wheat, jowar, maize, groundnut, 'dhan', 'gur', etc. These products are brought to the town mainly on bullock-carts by the farmers from neighbouring villages. The cart loads are directly purchased by the grain merchants. These products when collected are classified according to the quality and are exported by the motor trucks to other parts of India. Maize and Jowar are mainly exported to Indore and Ahmedabad where the supply is used for producing starch for cloth.

(b) Retail Marketing:—

The most important and main retail market is known here as the 'Bada bazar' lying along the main street joining 'Dwarikadhish Darwaza' with 'Lanka Darwaza'. The main marketing spine extends from 'Pipli Bazar' in the

north to 'Loha Bazar' in the south and other markets spread out in a rib like pattern from it. The 'Kasara Bazar' is another such rib on the west. A new market zone in coming up outside the 'Gindor Darwaza' comprising the six goods transport companies, four shops of motor parts, the workshops of automobile repairs and several small restaurants and tea-stalls.

Like other Indian market towns, Jhalrapatan is also developed as market of miscellaneous articles. But there may also be noted small specialised units like 'Loha Bazar', 'Sarafa', 'Kasara Bazar', 'Dhan mandi', 'Subzi mandi', etc.

(c) Nature of Shops:—

On the basis of nature of shops in various retail markets, generally three types are recognised, viz.

1. Number of types of shops included under the aforesaid three groups as follows:

- (a) *Commodity Shops*:—Groceries 38, Cloth 33, Sweets 23, Earthen pots 17, General merchandise 14, Grains 14, Jewellery 12, Medical Stores 4, Motor parts 4, Wine Stores 4, Fruits and vegetables 3, Book Stores 3, Fans and Sewing machines 2, Petrol-pumps 1.
- (b) *Service Shops*:—Tailors 32, Hair dressers 15, Laundries 12, Cycle repairs 10, Shoe-repairs 8, Goods transport 7, Workshops 2.
- (c) *Service-cum-sale Shops*:—Iron-smiths 32, Restaurants 24, Betel shops 18, Brass wares 18, Shoe-makers 16, Dyers 12, Goldsmiths 11, Cycle Stores 5, Radio dealers 2, Watch service 1, Photo Studio 1 and News papers 1.

(This classification is based on information gathered after enquiry on the spot during 1984).

(i) Commodity shops numbering 172, (ii) Service shops numbering 86 and (iii) Service-cum-sale shops numbering 141.

Of all the commodity shops, those of grocery dominate in number and are to be found not only in the main markets but are also scattered in the residential area. Though specialised markets do not exist yet the shops of cloth, confectionary and jewellery are found in groups in the main market. Such shops as cycle stores, medical stores, book stores and of electric fans and sewing machines are also scattered over the market zone but the four wine stores are 'suitably' placed on the four sides of the town. There are also mobile shops of edibles like the 'namkin-wala' and fruit-sellers who roam about in the various parts of the town for the whole day with their goods on cycle trollies.

Service shops are those where only some sorts of service is rendered to the customers, like tailoring, hair cutting saloon, laundry, repair of cycles, automobile workshops and goods transport agencies. The cobblers sitting by the road side may also be included in the above category. There are in all 86 such service establishments in the town.

In between the two groups of shops mentioned above there is

another group of the service-cum-sale shops where commodity is sold along with some sort of service. There are several streets abounding in particular artisan group, where the workshop and the shop are combined with the residential quarter of the artisan. There is thus a street known as the Kasara Bazar, where brass wares are not only manufactured and sold but are also repaired by the same person. Other such shops rendering service as well as selling are those of the goldsmiths, ironsmiths and shoe-makers. Restaurants and tea-stalls, like the omnipresent betel and cigarette shops are distributed all over the commercial zone.

The Periodical Markets:—

Apart from the permanent commercial activity of the town, there are other activities which though periodical in nature have been of great importance in the economic and commercial life of the town. These are the periodical weekly market and the fairs.

(a) The Weekly Market:

Monday is the market day when the periodic market locally known as 'hat' is organised by Municipality. People from rural areas bring such commodities as ghee, gur, vegetables or other agricultural products as head loads and sitting in front of the

shops in the Bada Bazar and Dhan

Mandi dispose of their goods. This is also the real day of 'sale' for urban shopkeepers who have to deal more with the rural folks who purchase the articles of their daily necessities such as 'bidis' or indigenous cigarettes earthen wares, cloth, agricultural implements, kerosine oil, salt and such other sundry articles.

(b) Fairs:

Two fairs are held within the municipal area of the town, beginning with the 'purnima' or the full moon day of the months of 'kartika' (Nov.) and 'Vaishakha' (April) respectively. Obviously these fairs are timed to be held immediately after the 'kharif' and 'rabi' harvests. The fairs of course draw many merchants and shops from outside, but the local business men, artisans in particular, prepare themselves to reap the commercial harvest as it were, during these fairs. The sale and purchase of the cattle, particularly of draft animals for agricultural work form the integral part of these fairs.

The Kartik fair which has also religious bearing is held for ten days and in the proximity of the Chandravati temples. The fair ground occupies a barren piece of land southwest of the walled town. The fair is organised in a planned manner and not only are the different sections allotted to the shops of different commodities

but other things as touring talkies and other means of recreation are given a fixed place.

The Vaishakha fair by Rana Madansingh is held only for a week. Being held in summer it has been sited in close proximity of Gomtisagar, along its northern boundary. The shops in the fair are erected along the road in a linear pattern and the rear is allotted for the cattle and means of recreation.

Source areas of Jhalrapatan

The market as a living organism depends for its vitality and growth upon its source areas which covers generally the surrounding region. In the present case although there is no precise boundary of the service area yet there are zones delimited by the source areas of agricultural products, vegetables, milk, etc. arriving to the market.

Among the services performed by the town, marketing and trading of agricultural products seem relatively more important because of the nature of the surrounding countryside comprising the northern extension of the Malwa plateau. The service area of the weekly market is conspicuously governed by the regional roads connecting the town in the immediate south with the Agarand Bakani and in the east with

Aklera. The limits of the source area of agricultural products correspond largely to the service areas of the weekly market and as such is enough to testify the rural base of the market. The southern extension of these cover nearly twelve miles, while their northern limits is restricted only by a distance of a mile. This may be explained by the presence of another important market of Jhalawar which is only four miles north of the town under study.

The milk and vegetable supply zones follow nearly the same circular pattern extending more towards the south than in the north. But the areal extension of these covers nearly one-fourth of the agricultural or weekly market's source areas because milk vegetables are not liable to be stored and are perishable products.

Conclusion:—

Jhalrapatan is one of those rural centres in the Hadaoti

plateau, where unique nodality has since its very inception made the town a flourishing trade centre. But certain problems have restricted the development of the town. Among them foremost is the difficulty of quick and easy transport because of its being located nearly 18 miles off the nearest railway track; some of the other problems are: the long periodicity of weekly market, lack of a suitable market place within the town and congestion of traffic converging on the market place.

There are immense future prospects for the development of Jhalrapatan as a market. It commands the region where agriculture is prosperous and groundnut is abundantly grown. Therefore, some agriculture based industries should be organised by the state government and allowed to develop here to give impetus to the trade and marketing. The periodic market may also be encouraged to take place twice in a week and proper, well built and spacious enclosure may be allotted for it.

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CROP COMBINATION TECHNIQUES—A SEARCH FOR AN IDEAL TOOL FOR APPLICATION TO MICRO-REGIONS

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Introduction:

The object of this paper is to analyse the existing advanced techniques for crop combination study and to evolve a suitable model for its application to any micro-region in India, so that proper emphasis can be given only to those crops which have got maximum combination at the police station or taluka level. Thus the policy of indiscriminate application of crop diversification scheme may be avoided. This has assumed greater importance when India is launching a massive programme of irrigation to turn the monocultural areas to double crop system to step up agricultural production. In quest of this tool, four techniques *1 have been analyzed and have been applied to the Mahanadi delta of Orissa where the same set of data has been used, as a case study. The data was collected by field investigation from the unpublished records of Government of Orissa.

Crop combination technique of Weaver:

The study of crop combination in the Mahanadi delta as per Weaver's technique has been taken up by the application of the standard deviation formula *2 which is as follows:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum d^2}{n}} \text{ or } \sigma^2 = \frac{\sum d^2}{n}$$

where σ = Deviation
 d = Difference from the standard
 n = Number of crops in given combination.

The above technique will be clear from the following table where the crop combination of Mahanga police station of Cuttack district where minimum deviation from the standard and three-crop combination occurs i.e. paddy (P), pulses (Pu) and jute (J). It is the sole instance for three-crop combination where as nine police stations have two-crop combination of P Pu and all other 14 police stations depict monoculture type where paddy dominates. At